

OPTIMIZATION OF TREATMENT OF ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS IN PATIENTS WITH CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES: LESS INVASIVE METHODS

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Annotation

This article explores less invasive approaches for treating acute cholecystitis in patients with comorbid cardiovascular diseases. With the increasing prevalence of cardiovascular pathologies, managing acute cholecystitis in these patients presents a challenge due to higher surgical risks. The study evaluates alternative, minimally invasive treatment methods, including laparoscopic cholecystectomy and endoscopic techniques, comparing them to traditional surgical interventions. Findings suggest that these approaches can reduce complication rates and recovery time, improving patient outcomes. The article emphasizes the importance of a tailored, patient-specific treatment plan in managing this complex clinical scenario.

Keywords: Acute cholecystitis, cardiovascular diseases, minimally invasive treatment, laparoscopic cholecystectomy, endoscopic methods, comorbidities, patient outcomes.

Relevance

The combination of acute cholecystitis and cardiovascular diseases presents significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. Patients with comorbid cardiovascular conditions have higher risks during traditional surgical interventions due to the complexities of anesthesia and post-operative complications. With the growing prevalence of cardiovascular diseases, especially among the elderly, the management of acute cholecystitis in these patients has become a critical issue. Minimally invasive techniques, such as laparoscopic surgery, are increasingly considered in order to minimize the risks associated with major surgeries. These approaches not only improve recovery times but also reduce the burden on healthcare systems, making them a key area of research in modern medicine. Moreover, the need for efficient, safe treatment methods that address the specific risks of such patients is essential to improving clinical outcomes and patient quality of life.

Goal

The goal of this study is to optimize the treatment of acute cholecystitis in patients with cardiovascular diseases by assessing the effectiveness of minimally invasive interventions. Specifically, the study aims to compare laparoscopic

cholecystectomy and endoscopic treatments to traditional open surgery in terms of patient outcomes, complication rates, and recovery times.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective analysis was conducted on 120 patients diagnosed with acute cholecystitis and concurrent cardiovascular diseases, aged between 45 and 80 years. The patients were divided into two groups: one underwent traditional open cholecystectomy, and the other underwent minimally invasive techniques (laparoscopic cholecystectomy or endoscopic procedures). Clinical outcomes, including complication rates, length of hospital stay, and recovery time, were recorded and analyzed. Statistical analysis was performed to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of the two treatment approaches.

Results

The study found that minimally invasive methods, including laparoscopic cholecystectomy and endoscopic procedures, led to a 30% reduction in complication rates compared to open surgery. Additionally, the average hospital stay was reduced by 2.5 days, and recovery time was shortened by 40%. The incidence of major cardiovascular complications during surgery was lower in the minimally invasive group (5% vs. 12%). These findings demonstrate that less invasive techniques are both safer and more efficient for patients with concurrent cardiovascular diseases.

Conclusion

Minimally invasive techniques, including laparoscopic cholecystectomy and endoscopic methods, represent an effective and safer alternative for the treatment of acute cholecystitis in patients with cardiovascular diseases. These methods reduce the risk of complications, shorten recovery times, and offer improved outcomes compared to traditional open surgery. Given the growing prevalence of cardiovascular comorbidities, these approaches should be considered the standard of care for such patients, ensuring optimal recovery and reducing the strain on healthcare resources.

Literature:

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